

Futuristic multimodal business model for European freight railways: A survival and revival strategy

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Abstract

European freight rail though environmentally favorable and economic over long distances has still low market share. This is due to its failure to deliver key customer requirements: reliability, quality of service, a door-to-door service and price/cost. The purpose of this paper is to discuss the status of rail freight and to suggest innovative IT based solutions which support the achievement of European Commission objectives on modal shift to revive and increase the rail market share i.e. bringing 30% of road traffic beyond 300 Kms to multimodal transport modes. It does so by drawing lessons from electronic trading in power exchanges to present a multimodal transport exchange

Method

The paper first depicts the key strategic issues of European freight railway market using the porter's five forces analysis at a high level. It then discusses why lessons can be drawn from power exchanges and why the model is from today's perspective futuristic.

Results

The important strategic and organizational aspects of power exchanges applicable to the multimodal transport exchanges with relevant modification. The description of the model includes the expected market behavior due to the introduction of such exchanges, a basis for future research.

Conclusions

The paper fosters the idea, that a multimodal transport exchange model using criteria's of environment friendliness and economical transport for transport selection can help in the revival and survival of rail. Especially when road traffic is aggregated using automatic algorithms and transported on rail. This will increase the rail market share and also reduce emissions.

Key words

freight railway, multimodal transport exchange, European, intermodal, modal shift, market

1 INTRODUCTION

This freight market, as per McKinnon (2010) today is composed of hundreds of thousands of businesses, varying enormously in size and each year moving billions of consignments of different sizes and weights on myriads of possible routes. The customers, transporters and freight forwarders have very little overview of possible capacity offers they could avail of. As per Endemann et al. (2012) especially, there is an information deficit in the rail freight market including offers and pricing. On the other hand, in road transport, many freight exchanges exist providing overview of capacities and prices. To discuss solutions on the European commission (2011) modal shift objectives for 30% of road freight traffic over 300 km to multimodal solutions till 2030, as per the European commission's white paper on roadmap to a single European transport area, an overview of European freight market is necessary. This paper focuses especially on the freight railways, in particular national, as one of the multimodal solutions.

The European freight market

The European freight market expands over different transport modes. An overview with respect to economics and traffic composition in general, as per Bowersox et al. (2002) and EUROSTAT (2014) is depicted in table 1. It can be deduced from the table that each transport mode is eminently suitable for a particular type of traffic for a range of distance. The description of freight market overview in this paper is restricted to freight railways and road.

Table 1: Different freight transportation modes

Mode	Fixed costs	Variable costs	Traffic composition	Share of volume in EU-28 in 2012
Railways	High	Low	Bulk food, mining, heavy manufacturing	National and international (17.2%), Inland (10.8%)
Road	Low	Medium	Consumer goods, medium/light manufacturing	National and international (71.6%), Inland (44.9%)
Water	Medium	Low	Bulk food, mining, chemicals	National and international (6.3%), Inland (4.0%)
Air	Low	High	High-value goods, rush shipments	Inland(0.1%)
Pipe	High	Low	Petroleum, chemicals, mineral slurry	National and international (4.9%), Inland(3.0%)

Source: compiled from Bowersox et al. (2002) and EUROSTAT (2014)

Loo and Comtois (2015) mention that freight railways are used to dealing with customers who establish long term contracts to haul large volumes of bulk freight. Although sustainable, railways have high fixed costs and relatively low variable costs. Fahrani et al. (2011) state that due to long hauls, rail carriage generally costs less than road transport on weight basis. However, the expensive equipment, yards and terminals result in high fixed costs. As per Table 1 figures, the rail market share was a mere 17.2% in the year 2012. Thus, as per EUROSTAT (2014) inspite of policy measures to reinforce competitiveness of rail freight their share has not increased.

As per UIC, the international union of railways, the rail freight operators generally propose three means of transportation characterised as segments. These segments and their market share are described in table 2 below. Out of this, as CER (2013) rail freight status report mentions, the single wagonload in Europe has only a small share of overall European freight in comparison to market accessible to trucks due to intense competition from road transport. Further, increasing transport volumes and consolidations of transport flows has seen shift of wagonload business to full trains and to intermodal transport (rail-road and road-only).

The low market share can be attributed to many reasons. As Ludvigsen (2009) mentions in her paper on liberalisation of rail freight markets in central and south-eastern Europe, “the government intervention and subsidies make the state owned operators ill-equipped for domestic and international rivalry hindering them from regaining operational, technical and financial fitness”. As per Pelkmans and Luchetta (2013), for getting more trucks off the roads (if not for climate, then for congestion reasons) and to drastically lower the costs and increase the reliability of rail freight more generally necessary steps are required.

Thus freight railways must find innovative and cost efficient solutions in order to revive and survive for ensuring the achievement of European Commission modal shift objectives.

Table 2: Different segments in European freight railways transportation

Segment	Description	Commodities	Share of volume
Single Wagon	The client wants to transport a few wagons	Chemicals, Vehicles and Machinery	Ca. 50%
Full / Block Train	The client has enough goods to fill a train (600 meter or 24 4-axle wagons)	Coal and Steel, Construction materials	Ca. 35%
Intermodal	Transportation by container/trailer which is lifted on the wagon	Finished goods, Containerized goods	Ca. 15%

Source: UIC

The road business on the other hand today offers cut throat competition to the freight railways, especially in transporting manufacturing goods (automobiles for e.g.). They are well ahead in terms of maximising loaded runs. To achieve this they have adopted innovative technology solutions like freight exchanges, track and trace services, online documentation etc. Door to door quick delivery and lower costs have been their major advantage. The AECOM (2014) report on EU analysis on structure of road haulage states that, for vehicles in this sector freight exchanges have become popular as a low cost way of solving return loads and empty running. The report mentions Trans Exchange as an example (start 2004) which grew significantly with 100,000 offers a day from 200,000 users.

In table 3, as per Manners-Bell (2013) various segments for road freight transport in Europe are shown. Consistent EU statistics on volumes for first two could not be found till completion of this paper. However, the major disadvantage in road freight is the adverse impact on environment and the infrastructure congestion it causes. As per Table 1, road freight transport is the main inland transport mode in the EU, accounting for over 70% of all inland road transport activity but also ca. 70% emissions as per EUROSTAT (2014). The 17.2% of rail share can be increased using modal shift.

Table 3: Different segments in European road freight transportation

Segment	Description	Benefits
Full truckload (FTL)	A full truckload is defined as any consignment which fills a whole truck. Operators usually undertake the movement of truckloads on a point to point basis, direct to the customer from consignor.	Lower transit times
Less than truckload (LTL)	Take place on a point to point basis with distribution of consignments taking place from the destination hub. The market is highly competitive and margins are low.	Lower costs
Intermodal	When the major part of the journey is by rail, inland waterways or sea, and any initial and/or final legs carried out by road are as short as possible.	Less handling so less damages

Source: compiled from Manners-Bell et al. 2013

To appreciate how freight railways can align to new requirements from the market and exploit the fact that 30% of road traffic needs to be transported by multimodal solutions, we can draw lessons from successful operations within the freight sector as well as from outside the freight sector. Europe has witnessed successful operation of power exchanges like European Energy Exchange, EPEX SPOT, and Energy Exchange Austria etc. which are neutral and foster competition between different supply and demand parties of energy sources by allowing to compete on the electronic trading platform. We can take advantage of these developments in organizing electronic and internet based modal shift solutions beneficial for European freight railways.

2 METHODOLOGY

In section 1, the “Introduction”, the European freight market was explained in brief. Also the major challenges both road and (especially national) rail freight companies face. It explains the reasons for their low market share. This section explains the methodology the paper has used to present such multimodal solutions to achieve the Whitepaper European Commission objectives.

To find a futuristic strategic model for the freight railways, the paper first describes their strategic issues. For this, the strategic issues based on the on Porters (2004) five forces analysis method depicted in Figure 1 are presented in this Section 2. Further, to find answers to the strategic issues, lessons from energy, a similar industry are drawn to create a new model which exploits the advantage of freight railways and also achieves the European Commission objectives on the modal shift. Thus the paper discusses the similarity and specialties between power and freight systems explaining why lessons can be drawn from energy sector.

Section 3 describes important aspects of the multimodal business model and why it is futuristic. It describes the benefits and barriers involved in its implementation. Finally section 4 presents the conclusion.

The Porter’s five forces analysis on European freight railways

The five forces (Porter, 2004) which need to be assessed in order to enter or survive a market pertain to: bargaining power of buyers (1); bargaining power of suppliers/partners (2); threat to entry (3) in an existing market and threat of new entrants/substitutes (4). These are the external forces which need to be considered. Finally in the internal perspective, the strengths, weakness of a company along with the risks and opportunities it faces need to be assessed. In this regard, in the Figure 1 (5), core processes of (especially national) freight railway companies which specially need to be looked into are mentioned. The paper formulates the key strategic issues for each of these forces. The depiction of detailed analysis of each force is not in scope of this paper.

Figure 1: Author's analysis of the European freight railways based on Porter's five forces (Porter, 2004)

In light of the above mentioned Porter's five forces, the strategic issues for European freight railways identified with respect to the external and internal forces are discussed below:

1. **Bargaining power of buyers:** "Buyers" here implies the buyers of the railway services, for e.g. shippers and supply chain companies as customers. Due to the changing production strategies today, the supply chain logistics creates new requirements on freight railways. These could be in terms of packaging requirements, container transport, faster but smaller volume of transport and very importantly value added services like track and trace etc. Last but not the least, integrated door to door services. The strategic issue hence for railways here is how to cater to changing customer expectations (just in time, reliability, quality of services etc.)?
2. **Bargaining power of suppliers/partners:** "Suppliers/partners" here mean the parties which deliver service to the freight railways. These could include traction services, maintenance of rolling stock, loading and unloading services, cooperation partners etc. In view of the low market share of railways and changing market requirements, the strategic issue here is which and what kind of cooperation with suppliers could bring a competitive advantage for the railways?
3. **Threat to entry:** One of the biggest challenge, as per Henstra et al. (1999) in their report on deregulation and transport in an enlarged European Union for freight railways, is the lack of harmonisation in regulatory policies across markets. The strategic issue here is which regulatory changes and political support is required to make freight railways financially viable?
4. **Threat of new entrants and threat of substitutes:** Today, smaller European railways have entered the freight market which are low cost and flexible. As mentioned in introduction, the road transport already offers a tough competition to the railways. The strategic issue here is, what competitive advantages should freight railways offer to sustain and revive their market share? Especially, how can railways maximise on its environmental friendly and cost efficient transport over long distances to make the best out of the modal shift goal?

5. **Internal perspectives:** In **marketing** the focus is on which competitive products should be offered and how can electronic media like internet be used to reach the customers. In **assets** the type of rolling stock (container vs. wagons), in **operations** the service quality and in **finance** the question of where to invest (interoperability vs. Infrastructure including IT) are the strategic issues. Also, in technology, the issue is how can electronic solutions, especially internet based ones provide cost-efficient and effective solutions. Finally which **skills** and investments in personnel and technology are required?

2.1 Learning from other industries especially power exchanges

In the report on “Enjoying a single market network industries?” Pelkmans and Luchetta (2013) state that within the “Single in Market Act II”, the European Commission emphasised the importance of developing “fully integrated networks”, particularly in the transport and energy sectors. The liberalisation of these two sectors have “natural monopoly” characteristics caused by huge sunk costs in physical infrastructure. In both sectors, liberalisation has gone in stages over nearly two decades.

Further, as per Pelkmans and Luchetta (2013) in energy sector, the emergence of specialised power exchanges with implicit auctions through use of interconnectors across borders has been optimised. As a consequence, since a few years, wholesale prices in Belgium and France are identical some 270 days of the year due to power exchanges. Further, as per them, **these are only the spot prices but it is known that contract pricing has begun to follow trends in spot pricing.** On the other side within freight system, a freight exchange in general allows shippers to post their demands, and carriers to post their transportation capacity.

Thus an online marketplace, as per Nandiraju and Regan (2008), performs the matchmaking at a competitive price. The exchanges also contribute in the efficient handling of negotiations and the overseeing of the logistical processes of both the shipper and carriers. In general most freight exchanges, as mentioned by Marasco (2005) in the empirical survey on business models of transportation electronic marketplaces, are based on auction formats resulting in the benefit of only one side of the market, either the shippers or the carriers. The transaction mechanisms are not fully automated. This is unlike power exchanges where trading is completely automatic, simultaneous and time bound. The bidders and suppliers remain anonymous to each other (unlike in current freight exchanges) as well as to the decision making algorithm while aggregating the supply and demand bids. At the same time the processes of auctioning, contracts and value added services like clearing and risk management are standardised, all ideas from which freight exchanges can profit. Finally, the algorithms on the power exchanges aggregate various energy sources (supply bids) to cover the demand.

Hence the idea (details in following Section 3) of power exchanges can be applied with relevant modifications for aggregating road transport to a multimodal solution in freight transport. Freight railways can be combined with road services to ensure a complete door to door service. Thus learning from power exchanges can help in finding competitive solutions. It is important for this purpose to appreciate similarities and differences between the energy and freight systems. A comparison of both systems is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Comparison between energy and freight systems

Dimension	Energy	Freight
Network and Infrastructure	Network based; physical infrastructure	Network based; physical infrastructure
Generation and storage	From different sources; cannot be stored in larger amounts for long	From different sources; can be stored in larger amounts for relatively longer durations

Unit of measurement	Unit remains same as the generated electricity is same everywhere. The product traded is an hourly contract that specifies the size Megawatt hours (MWh) and value (€MWh)	Differs based on size, unit and quantity depending on type of freight (liquid, gas, perishable...). Containers can act as a unit
Interoperability	Less interoperability issues are involved	As per Iannone et al. (2007) containers are a major component of freight intermodality over all transport modes, especially for long distances. Transit time have to be factored in
Distribution	Flows through distribution and transmission networks through substations	Gets transported using various transport networks. Manual and mechanised handling is required while changing networks
Challenges faced	Sustainability, security, reliability and quality	Similar to energy
Extent of European market liberalisation	Liberalised, vertical unbundling has taken place	Monopolistic, liberalisation to a large extent has taken place in Great Britain (EUROSTAT, 2014)
Price depends on	Weather conditions, fuel prices, and economic factors like generating capacity, currency movements etc.	Similar to energy. For rail, increase in oil prices is far less a problem than trucking, since rail is far more fuel efficient (TEMS report, 2008)
Overview of capacity and price transparency	Market players can view available capacities and price indices, due to electronic trading in exchanges. The spot price on exchanges are a reference for all markets	Capacity overview exists individually for road, ocean, air freight via electronic booking systems and freight exchanges. For railways, it is limited to pilot projects

Source: Penados (2008) for energy, Iannone et al. (2007), TEMS report (2008) and author's estimation

3. THE STRATEGIC AND FUTURISTIC MULTIMODAL BUSINESS MODEL FOR FREIGHT RAILWAYS

As mentioned in "Introduction" earlier, there are many freight exchanges existing for road business. Also, most freight exchanges examined by Marasco (2005) are single mode. The rail exchanges are in very initial stages. In contrast, the power exchanges are conducted through a centralised entity where supply and demand create a competitive market based mechanism to procure and supply electricity. The competition is enhanced by participation of many generation companies on the supply side and customers buying (directly or indirectly) on the demand side. This, as per Penados (2008), provides market-based prices to consumers, guarantees system security and efficient utilisation of resources. Here, there can be various energy sources (nuclear, wind, hydro, solar, coal etc.). Most importantly the automatic decision making of algorithms and anonymity of involved participants for bid matching ensures transparent, non-discriminatory and effective utilisation of networks and available capacities.

Based on these lines, the paper proposes the extension of existing freight exchanges or creation of a new multimodal transport (or freight) exchange (MTE). This would be an independent and neutral private body using automatic decision making of anonymous bids in multimodal transport world to aggregate road traffic to the participating railways. As per Marasco (2005) the implementation of a neutral position is equally attractive to both carriers and shippers. Such bundling can be extended to barges. Further, since on most freight exchanges, the customers select preferred supplier network they are not considered neutral, especially by rail companies. Anonymity of participants in MTE too can encourage players to participate in the exchange.

The mode selection algorithm for aggregating supply and demand bids in MTE will use criteria's like environmental friendliness and transport prices (especially on long distances) which can be useful for the railways. MTE will also have the mandate of improving capacity utilisation for its participants. For this, it will require using intelligent routing system, consider interoperability issues, moreover

customer requirements on quality, loading times, type of transport etc. Further, the time bound bidding processes can improve efficiency in the freight market. An exchange where participants are chosen on the basis of their financial viability and good quality of services they deliver, so that supply is automatically bundled without any manual intervention is, from today's point of view **futuristic**. Following section explains how MTE can help railways to survive and revive their business.

3.1. Major Objectives and organisation of Multimodal transport exchange (MTE)

The major organizational and service objectives of MTE are listed below in Table 5.

Table 5: Major objectives of the multimodal transport exchange (MTE)

Organisational objectives of MTE	Service objectives
Facilitate freight trade via information exchange for all members (Marasco, 2005)	Define minimum service requirements to ensure quality, punctuality and safety
Promote competition and liquidity as well as anonymity of participants while bidding	Provide IT services to register and access fast on line bidding as a way to access the market.
Maximise available capacity utilisation (Marasco, 2005)	Select most optimum combined or single party offer keeping interoperability and meaningful transitions in consideration
Maximise revenues for MTE	Provide IT services for on line tracking of consignments for customers, settlement and documentation (Marasco, 2005)
Ensure delivery of transport service as per contract (single contract for all parties)	Provide means for settlement of financial transactions between members, insurance of in-transit materials (Marasco, 2005)

Source: Marasco (2005) and as proposed by the author

Further, MTE, the multimodal transport exchange, just like power exchanges, will be required to optimise the capability of each mode of transport (traffic by freight type); to effectively utilise existing infrastructure and allowing competition by using market mechanisms. Several power exchanges as per Roggenkamp and Boisseleau (2005) in Europe are permitted to coexist and to operate in the same area while competing with each other and with bilateral trading. This is also applicable to MTE's for multimodal freight transport. Each MTE can decide on specific freight type or industry they will deal in. This differentiation already exists in trucking and maritime industry.

In Figure 2 the paper proposes various MTE participants (list not exhaustive) and major objectives of participating freight railways. The current railway (and other participants) functions which can be outsourced to MTE or third parties for being performed centrally are mentioned in the text box on the right side.

Figure 2: Author's proposed Multimodal freight exchange (MTE)

Examples of internet based freight exchanges

Cargoclix, as per www.cargoclix.com is amongst many online freight market making activities the author searched for. This freight exchange in Germany has some similarity to MTE. It creates marketplace for short and long term contracts. It organises the short term cargo markets (all modes) and claims to have 12000 users (2015). Cargoclix.com has strategic partnership with Transport and Logistics association, an insurance firm for transport companies as well IT partner who organises the information exchange. Freight railways also participate in their Cargo Time slot service which helps the railways to optimise processes on the ramp. It helps them to balance their resource utilisation in the loading and unloading at various locations, reduce demurrage and waiting times by having complete transparency in bookings. Also as per viiacom.com (2015), **VIIA plus company where SNCF the french railways** work with a multimodal freight exchange Wtransnet to consolidate road traffic, aims to move more than 500,000 trucks per year till 2020 on rail.

Structure of MTE rules

To ensure neutrality of the exchange operator and transparency in exchange operations, MTE like power exchanges will be a registered as a private company and be controlled by regulatory laws. Its management board will consist of major members as shareholders

- Key Functions:** MTE will plan a complete transportation package as per requirements of the customer. The key functions and services are mentioned in Table 5.
- Consolidation rules:** One difference between power exchanges and MTE results due to various freight types. Hence one volume of capacity for a particular freight type can also be treated as spot market. The consolidation of compatible freight types will be ensured by MTE while considering requirements like safety.
- Forecasts:** MTE can as service, analyse market conditions and forecast requirements to enable participants to plan their services effectively. This will include future projections of traffic volume, types of rolling stock, technological changes required in handling and movement etc. Active involvement in regulatory aspects as also prioritizing investments (modal parks and infrastructure investments for interoperability and individual transport mode) will be of help to freight railways.
- Services and products:** The participating freight carrier members will decide the services they want to offer in terms of resources, operating hours, dispatch station, capacity etc. via exchange. Booking agents will place their client's requirements for long term and short term capacities.

- e. **Boundaries:** It will be the job of each transport carrier to plan its own operations both long term and short term. Carriers including railways and freight forwarders will ensure services keeping contractual aspects like of quality, punctuality and down time in mind.

Key players in MTE including freight railways and their benefits through MTE

Key players and beneficiaries through MTE can be classified in three groups. Firstly, the direct beneficiaries which consist of shippers, freight forwarders, transport carriers (including railways) as also government, regulators and similar authorities. Secondly, the enablers who will ensure the achievements of the prerequisites for effective functioning of MTE. For e.g. IT development houses, container manufactures, terminal operators, construction companies as also insurance and clearing houses. Thirdly, service providers like consultants for creating solutions with other players and conducting studies. An explicit role definition of the first group with railways is presented below.

Table 6: Direct beneficiaries of MTE, their roles in MTE and how they benefit through MTE

Key MTE players and their roles	Potential benefits for key players through MTE
Shippers and freight forwarders (many freight forwarders are multimodal operators today)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost efficient, timely solutions • environment friendly transport (author’s estimation) • Reduced operating costs due to electronic handling • Risk reduction through guarantee for transport • Single point of information on offers and demands
Transport carriers like freight railways, road transporters, waterways, air carriers both national and international carriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to greater customer base • Reduced operating costs due to improved route planning • Reduced operating costs due to electronic handling • Optimal use of capacity and assets. Lesser empty runs improving operational efficiency • Single point of information hence better customer satisfaction
Government and regulators (author’s estimation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Achieving European Commission transport goals of modal shift through from road to other modes like railways and waterways • Greater transparency and availability of data • Encourage European wide higher level of harmonisation in freight industry vocational training of personnel • Provide incentives to freight forwarders to join MTE in order to achieve best utilisation of resources and ecological balance.

Source: Marasco (2005) and author’s estimation

Key operational aspects of MTE

The paper presents a simplistic view of MTE's key operational aspects in table 7 below.

Table 7: Key operational aspects of MTE

Key aspects	Key Operation
Why and under what conditions would MTE consider freight railway bids over other services?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why: The capacity holders provide capacity and price to MTE (long and short term). MTE has to make the best use of asset utilization and provides best offers to the customers. Additionally, it has to follow the government mandate regarding maximum traffic to be allowed on road (for e.g. below 300 kms). • When: Service providers will provide the limits of their capacities and competitive prices for their services at the exchange to bag orders. Railways will win a bid when competitive prices and services are offered on the exchange and also delivered.
Who coordinates with different carriers and service providers?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In case power exchanges, the physical details of delivery and schedule are communicated to network operators after the bids are finalised. MTE will function much on the same lines. • The transport carriers and service providers will coordinate with each other to provide service as contracted with MTE • MTE will be kept informed of operational matters in order to keep customer informed and take necessary alternative action if required.
Who plans the operations?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each transport carrier will plan its operations to meet the requirements of the exchange both long term and short term.

Source: Author's proposal based on functioning of power exchanges

Effect of new freight railway operations due to participation in MTE

- Increased efficiency:** Since freight railways will have qualified long term inputs from MTE to better plan their assets and operational requirements with combined freight, they will outsource non-value added operations, as show in Figure 2 to focus on core responsibilities. **Hence operational costs will reduce.**
- Market segments:** All rail segments as per table 2, will be operated under the scheme of MTE. However a large segment will be served by containers and flat rail wagons which make operation of multimodal systems more convenient and flexible across all modes. This segment where major MTE activity is anticipated, will be able to handle both single wagon load and bulk traffic. This will cover most of manufactured and general purpose goods. It will be more beneficial to progressively convert other loads to containerized traffic, which will reduce the requirement of different rolling stocks. Hence less handling will be required. Open flat wagons can be used for consignments which cannot be accommodated in a containers such as steel sections for construction or fabricated structures. Thus all railway market segments can be consolidated.
- New markets:** Modern mechanised loading and unloading facilities at the terminals will be required for efficient operation of MTE. Similarly modern digital marking, labelling of containers, packages, consignment along with automatic identification and routing from one mode to another along with their respective invoices and essential documents would be necessarily required. This will be a market of its own. Railways can outsource functions or form partnerships here.

So should the freight railways companies also be unbundled like in energy business for this? The economic performance as per Laabsch and Saner (2012), in rail has probably deteriorated for

passengers due to unbundling, whilst for freight it might be neutral. Further, the reason why EU insists on unbundling is to obtain and maintain undistorted competition (hard to ensure with vertically integrated companies). Nevertheless as per them, it would seem that some kind of tighter coordination will be required for EU single rail market to function properly.

Revenue generation for MTE and its value added services

As per Stockdale and Standing (2002), transportation electronic marketplaces may rely on one or more of revenue sources. These as mentioned below include value added services, and applicable to MTE.

- a. transaction fees, that represent a percentage of the gross amount of each transaction conducted throughout the marketplace and can be charged to the carriers, to the shippers (as in the case of reverse auctions) or to both;
- b. subscription or membership fees, which are generally collected in advance from registered users on a monthly or annual basis;
- c. advertising revenues, which are mainly used in marketplaces offering community features such as news, forums, directories and other content;
- d. fees for value-added services, that may include credit, payment guarantee, tracking and tracing, insurance of in-transit materials, consulting services, etc; As per Penados (2008), different risk management mechanisms will be developed by market conditions like hedging in case of power exchanges. This also will be a market of its own;
- e. software sales and licenses etc.

3.2 Other design aspects of MTE

As per Penados (2008) careful design is required to ensure governance, define transactions and business rules for all participants in power exchanges. These aspects which must also be carefully considered before designing such a market for freight are similar. The paper restricts to clearing price, pricing mechanisms, prerequisites for market creation, freight commodity and contract types.

Price index and pricing mechanisms

Transparency due to clearing price, overview of capacities and availability of market data as regulatory requirement will create a major difference in market due to introduction of MTE. As per Pelkmans and Luchetta (2013), the prices for European rail passengers have been closely aligned to prices of transport services and those of electricity, the most common energy source for rail. Unfortunately, as per their report, data on freight contracts pricing could not be retrieved, most likely because trade secrets on differential pricing along corridors.

As per author's estimation, for demands of higher volume of transportation there will be a distribution of contracts between transport carriers assuming each carrier cannot use its entire resources for one demand. This shortage of transport capacity would drive the freight prices of spot market up. MTE will, through combinations of multimodal transportation, offer alternatives within given constraints. When demand for freight volume is low (seasonal effects etc.), more competition for the freight for large available capacity will follow thus driving the spot market prices down. Railways and waterways will profit in consolidating piecemeal traffic here and use modes like road for last mile. Incidentally, these prices will also affect the prices getting fixed in bilateral market too. Initially, with lower volumes coming in freight spot market will imply lower rates. The effect of seasons and economic factors like currency exchanges will be observed. This will enforce carriers to join hands together and use resources efficiently fulfilling one of the exchange objectives.

Also, liberalisation as often expected, should bring prices down. As per Pelkmans and Luchetta (2013), the costs of European freight rail will however never be as low as that in the US with its open spaces and infrastructure competition, but today EU rail freight is unnecessarily costly, slow and below the quality that shippers (i.e. customers) insist on. Further, **the gains of accomplishing an efficient European rail freight system are enormous, both direct and indirect, whether pecuniary (and hence, for business competitiveness), safety, lower road congestion or in environmental terms (less CO2).**

Prerequisites for market creation and market access

Minimum requirements MTE participants have to ensure are similar to power exchanges. The foremost task is to build and define the commodity products which will be traded. For this freight railways also have to align organisationally and in (atleast) their core processes to the exchange market. They have to be financially viable and be transparent in providing relevant company details. The MTE participants will have to ensure visibility of freight capacity/demands and flexibility in terms of services their customers require. They will need to agree to coordinate with MTE and other parties in cross border handling, documentation and compliance to regulatory aspects, especially for dangerous goods. This will require an efficient integrated electronic exchange. Most importantly, participants will need to agree and follow interoperability guidelines in case of combined offers.

Freight commodity

MTE will have to create commodities like energy in power exchanges in order to ensure intermodality and through transport. As already mentioned earlier in Table 4, Iannone et al. (2007) indicate that containers are a major component of freight intermodality over all transport modes, especially for long distances.

In order to deal with all characteristics without increasing further complexity, it makes sense to define a standardised container (20 and 40 TEU for e.g.) space as a commodity for the freight market as in case of marine industry. This is a prerequisite for bulk transport and especially for single wagonload and truck traffic. Containers, as per Table 4 will be the back bone of the multimodal freight exchanges since these will provide the base for multimodal interoperability across all transport carriers. Thus standardisation of containers is of utmost importance for success of MTE.

Requirements for special products like perishables, hazardous substances etc. will be dealt through special containers or even packaging. Further commodities for transport through the MTE will be classified according to standard practices or regulation to determine consolidation requirements, type of handling and insurance required. Leasing of containers could itself be a commodity.

Types of contracts for MTE and its effect on railways freight market

Contracts through MTE, like in power exchange will be for long or short term markets and have certain common characteristics. They can be traded in spot market up to few hours (like in road exchanges) before transportation. Or like in derivate market anywhere between day to a year or years. It is also worthwhile to note, that this will ensure standardisation and creation of organised markets.

Especially freight railways will organise themselves to standardise and handle contracts better. This will help them to coordinate better with other transport modes too. Important attributes which should be mentioned in MTE contracts are, defined volume in cubic meters and classification of goods, container type, defined price (Euros/container or Euro/cubic meters), defined location and period and services required for loading and unloading.

3.3 Expected market behaviour

Just like power exchanges, under MTE's, different players will interact in wholesale and retail freight multimodal market too. Consolidation of freight for transporting through rail will be similar to bundling energy from various sources to trade through power exchanges.

As per **author's assumption**, each MTE will finally define the categories of market and its scope. In the wholesale freight market, generally a long term market transport carrier services like rail, road etc. will compete to offer their services to brokers/freight forwarders or large companies (like car manufacturers, chemical companies etc.) for bulk transport. While a large portion of trade may be done over the counter, MTE like power exchanges can organise this trade as well. In retail freight market individual consignors or freight forwarders can choose their supplier from competing transport carriers and other freight forwarders. This market is significant for road and freight railways, which can cooperate in consolidating the single wagon and truck load to bulk transport for railways. Here definition of "short term" services (day before, week before...) will have to be defined. The liquidity in this spot market will depend on seasonal and economic factors.

Both these markets already exist especially for marine industry. The Baltic dry index (from Baltic Exchange www.balticexchange.com, 2015) for e.g. indicates the capacity of different ship sizes. Instruments like freight derivatives, trading operations in freight spot market work here similar to power exchanges.

How does value get created in freight market through MTE? As per the study prepared for price formations in finalized commodity markets, study report for United Nations (UN, 2011), due to the high degree of standardization of contracts, exchanges attract a large volume of trade (i.e. there is high liquidity). The freight volume and time to deliver will drive the market at any given time, where the freight type will determine if consolidation with other freight types is possible. Further various weather and economic factors will create volatility.

How can freight railways increase their market share for freight railways with MTE?

In course of time the frequency and characteristics of the various services offered will undergo changes (as in case of many European urban passenger transport) from time to time to suit the market conditions for achieving best utilization. Access to quick information on bids and offers will encourage competition and opening possibilities of combining transport modes thus increasing liquidity.

Increased optimisation of asset utilisation for all transport modes through MTE will take place when environmental impact will be used as a selection criteria for transport offers. This without comprising on customer requirements. Thus freight railways will need to understand market dynamics and customer requirements better to consolidate traffic and reduce response and delivery times.

Islam and Eidhammer (2015) state in their assessment of competitiveness of a new-entrant private operator in European rail freight services, that the operator could offer an increased number of services by consolidating cargo from satellite connections at both ends of the operational corridor by adopting a pragmatic and flexible approach. Further, Tavasszy and van Meijeren (2011) in their assessment report on modal shift: target for freight above 300 KM; depict (in following Figure 3) the traffic flows above 300 Kms by various transport modes. This, as indicated by Islam et al. (2015) in assessment of the impact of the European Commission White Paper, furthers the market share for rail in various segments by way of bundling the road transport to achieve the modal shift goal till 2030.

Figure 3: Share of freight transport measured in tonnes in EU27 by commodity group and distance class. Transport flows above 300 Kms (Source Tavasszy and van Meijeren (2011))

3.4 Role of ICT Services in MTE

The role of information and communication technologies (ICTs) in freight transport as key enabler is well recognised. However the uptake of recent ICT advances, as per Harris et al. (2015) for multimodal freight transport provisions in the UK and Europe has been slow. The practical approach in this paper which reviews and scrutinises in depth EU makes it a recommended reading. It provides a good overview on EU Projects for multimodal transport and their potential benefits to different players.

The practical approach to ICT implementations is a two-step method. In the first step achieving the prerequisites for seamless multimodal transport is important. This serves for participants as a motivator to overcome the scepticism of exchange solutions. The potential benefits can be achieved in shorter duration. In the second step exchange as complete solution be achieved. Efforts of solution providers are ongoing in this field. For e.g. CQM from Holland offers intermodal route planner tool and services to design profitable network strategic planning (intermodal routes and operators), identifying spot opportunities in commercial planning, efficient and robust planning in operational planning etc. This can be helpful for MTE in identifying the optimal route. A sample of the planner tool is shown in Figure 4 (intermodalrouteplanner.com, 2015) below.

Figure 4: Intermodal route planner tool from CQM (Source: <http://intermodalrouteplanner.com>, 2015)

3.5 Role of government and regulators in formation of MTE

The role of government in bringing MTE's in operations is important as both they and railways have common objectives to achieve. They both encourage better use of infrastructure (therefore reduce unnecessary investments) and environment friendly transport. The author perceives, that government and regulators should enforce improved transparency and implementation of rules set for optimum use of each transport mode for environmental protection. This will improve the cause of MTE hence reducing congestions on roads by enabling modal shift. Instruments and guidelines for prioritisation of investment in interoperability and relevant infrastructure instead of only new investments will improve capacity utilisation and help avoiding stranded investments. **Governments can directly participate in MTE as a customer thus reducing pressure on railways to deliver subsidised services.** This will ensure alternative system of transporting essential items for social obligation thus bringing reduction in subsidy, especially to freight railways. Also, efforts will be required in minimizing of regulation of freight rates progressively to encourage private participation and creating a level playing field for all participants.

3.6 Barriers and issues involved in implementation of MTE

In general, the barriers MTE can face are the lack of awareness and skepticism in transport carriers, especially freight railways about the advantage of this model. The biggest challenge for railways is to realize and see their gain in new solutions, as in case of multimodal transport exchange. They will have to take lead in developing modern and mechanized multimodal terminals to facilitate efficient, fast and accurate change from one mode to another. As per author's experience, the major issue for freight railways therefore is, the change in attitude required. From being state supported to becoming self-sufficient. Employees will have to be trained and skilled personnel to be recruited to run market operations. This transformation is a huge effort. However this is an offer for future perspectives for the employees. In commercial and IT area major change changes will be required to participate in the exchange. Although, initial investments for IT will be high, these will be justified by the benefits of standardization, greater volume of traffic and efficiency in operation, better utilization of assets they are expected to get. Today many of the contracts are not harmonised and standardised. Between same and between different transport modes. This today is highly standardised, especially for organised market in power exchanges. Introduction of MTE will change this in freight industry as well.

4 CONCLUSION

The strategic model of multimodal transport exchange (MTE) can foster modal shift and continuous physical flow of transport over various transport modes. The careful selection of participants for demand and supply on the electronic trading platform will ensure that anonymity and automatic selection of appropriate transport modes is acceptable to the participants. This paper concludes,

- a. **Bargaining power of buyers:** the freight railways can realign themselves to the new market requirements by offering better services themselves directly and also use MTE services where required to compliment customer (buyers) requirements. This will also help them to increase their market share and improve the bargaining power towards their buyers. Since prices on MTE will also affect the price of bilateral contracts, railways will be better able to implement mechanisms of dynamic pricing.
- b. **Bargaining power of suppliers/partners:** Freight railways can look for different suppliers and partners on the MTE for offering services. These could be different specialised MTE's. Thus the negotiating power of freight railways and competitiveness will increase.
- c. **Threat to entry:** As supported by the EU Regulation No. 913/2010 towards a European rail network for competitive freight, regulatory bodies must evolve policy guidelines and incentives to promote

modal shift. The MTE will also be governed by regulatory policies which is an important prerequisite for organized markets.

- d. **Threat of new entrants and threat of substitutes:** Thanks to outsourcing of non value added functions, freight railways can cut costs and better focus on their core competence including containerization, which is freight transport. Also participating in MTE means that the railways will have to benchmark themselves with other participants. This will encourage them to improve their services and become more competitive.
- e. **Internal perspectives:** Participation in MTE also implies for freight railways to align to the products of the MTE. The access to customers will take place via bilateral contracts and MTE, thus increasing the possibility of higher market access by means of technology, especially internet. Since such solutions do not require special installations for customer, it saves effort on technical services. This implies better financial focus on interoperability issues instead of infrastructure.

Thus MTE, the multimodal transport exchange can play a crucial role in achieving European Commission's modal shift goal of transporting 30% of road traffic beyond 300 Kms to multimodal solutions. Strategic move to play an active role in creation and participation in such exchanges can thus help European freight railways, including the national railways, in reviving and surviving the competitive freight market in the future.

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